

1 The Aegean Sea as driver of hydrographic and ecological
2 changes in the eastern Mediterranean

3 **Gianluca Marino***

4 *Institute for Coastal Marine Environment, National Research Council, Porto di Napoli,*
5 *Calata Porta di Massa, 80133 Naples, Italy*

6 **Eelco J. Rohling**

7 *National Oceanography Centre, Southampton, Hampshire SO14 3ZH, UK*

8 **W. Irene C. Rijpstra**

9 *Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ), Department of Marine*
10 *Biogeochemistry & Toxicology, PO Box 59, Den Burg, Texel, Netherlands*

11 **Francesca Sangiorgi**

12 *Palaeoecology, Institute of Environmental Biology, Laboratory of Palaeobotany and*
13 *Palynology, Utrecht University, Budapestlaan 4, 3584 CD Utrecht, Netherlands, and the*
14 *Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ), Department of Marine*
15 *Biogeochemistry & Toxicology, PO Box 59, Den Burg, Texel, Netherlands*

16 **Stefan Schouten**

17 **Jaap S. Sinninghe Damsté**

18 *Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ), Department of Marine*
19 *Biogeochemistry & Toxicology, PO Box 59, Den Burg, Texel, Netherlands*

20 *E-mail: G.Marino@uu.nl; currently also at: Palaeoecology, Institute of Environmental
21 Biology, Laboratory of Palaeobotany and Palynology, Utrecht University, Budapestlaan
22 4, 3584 CD Utrecht, Netherlands.

23 **ABSTRACT**

24 The eastern Mediterranean (eMed) is experiencing a long-term increase in net
25 evaporation, which may have preconditioned the profound changes that occurred in its
26 deep-sea ventilation over the past two decades. We test the sensitivity of Aegean
27 convective deep-water formation to forcing in the opposite sense, based on a last
28 interglacial episode of enhanced freshwater injection into the eMed. We find that Aegean
29 subsurface ventilation collapsed completely within 40 ± 20 yr, promoting euxinic
30 conditions, hostile to aerobic life, which expanded toward the photic layer within $650 \pm$
31 250 yr. Another 300 ± 120 yr later, similar conditions extended throughout the eMed.
32 These findings emphasize the exceptional sensitivity of Aegean deep-water formation to
33 climatic forcing, driving large-scale hydrographic adjustments throughout the eMed, and
34 beyond.

35 **Keywords:** Mediterranean Sea, thermohaline circulation, sapropels, stable isotopes,
36 biomarkers.

37 **INTRODUCTION**

38 On a global scale, new deep-water formation delivers oxygen to the deep-sea. In
39 the eastern Mediterranean (eMed), this process has long been dominated by the sinking
40 and spreading of Adriatic dense waters (Malanotte-Rizzoli and Hecht, 1988). The late
41 1980s-early 1990s witnessed an abrupt shift to dominance of Aegean Deep-Waters in the
42 eMed deep-sea ventilation (Eastern Mediterranean Transient, EMT) (Roether et al., 1996;
43 Klein et al., 1999; Malanotte-Rizzoli et al., 1999), which eventually influenced even the
44 density of Mediterranean outflow into the Atlantic (Millot et al., 2006). Several studies
45 conclude that this profound hydrographic reorganization was preconditioned by a long-

46 term increase in eMed net evaporation (Béthoux et al., 1998; Boscolo and Bryden, 2001;
47 Skliris and Lascaratos, 2004; Skliris et al., 2007). Other studies emphasize the role of
48 synoptic changes in the wind field affecting upper thermocline circulation and, in turn,
49 the salt supply to the Aegean Sea (Malanotte-Rizzoli et al., 1999; Samuel et al., 1999;
50 Stratford and Haines, 2002).

51 We investigate the sensitivity of the Aegean thermohaline circulation to a
52 reduction of eMed net evaporation due to freshwater flooding, using a key example of the
53 organic-rich layers (sapropels) that periodically occur in the eMed sedimentary archive.
54 Sapropels reflect periods of sluggish bottom-water ventilation in response to enhanced
55 monsoon-fuelled river discharge along the North-African margin (e.g., Rohling et al.,
56 2002; Emeis et al., 2003). Last interglacial sapropel S5 is intensely developed and holds
57 excellent potential for highly resolved studies (Cane et al., 2002; Rohling et al., 2002,
58 2004, 2006). However, a lack of Aegean S5 records has to date limited our understanding
59 of the hydrographic responses in this critical region to a sharp reduction in eMed net
60 evaporation.

61 Here we present the first systematic high-resolution multi-proxy study of an
62 Aegean S5, as retrieved from south-eastern Aegean core LC21 (Fig. 1). Results are
63 discussed within the context of previously described contemporaneous records from the
64 open eMed ODP site 971A (Cane et al., 2002; Rohling et al., 2002, 2004, 2006).

65 MATERIAL AND METHODS

66 Core LC21 was recovered in 1995 by *RV Marion Dufresne* for the EC-MAST2
67 PALAEOFLUX program. We analyzed S5, in sections 5 and 6, at 1 cm (decadal)
68 resolution for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in *Globigerinoides ruber* (white) and *Neogloboquadrina*

69 *pachyderma* (dextral), and at 5 cm (centennial) resolution for alkenone-based sea surface
70 temperatures (SSTs), total organic carbon (C_{org}), and isorenieratene concentrations (Data
71 Repository Fig. DR1¹).

72 Stable isotope analyses were performed in Southampton with a Europa Geo2020
73 dual inlet mass spectrometer following individual acid-bath reaction of 15–20 handpicked
74 and cleaned specimens in the size ranges 300–350 μm (*G. ruber*) and 250–300 μm (*N.*
75 *pachyderma*). Isotope ratios are expressed as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, in ‰ values relative to
76 Vienna PeeDee Belemnite (VPDB). External precision was better than 0.06 ‰ for both
77 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$.

78 C_{org} contents, alkenone analyses, and isorenieratene concentrations were
79 performed at NIOZ. C_{org} contents were determined on decalcified sediments, using a
80 Carlo Erba Flash elemental analyzer coupled to a Thermofinnigan DeltaPLUS irmMS
81 system. For alkenone analysis freeze-dried and homogenized sediments were extracted
82 using Dionex™ accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) technique using dichloromethane
83 (DCM)/methanol (2:1, v/v) at 100 °C and 7.6×10^6 Pa. The extracts were separated by
84 Al_2O_3 column chromatography using first hexane/DCM (9:1, v/v) and then hexane/DCM
85 (1:1, v/v) to elute the alkenone fraction, which was analyzed by gas chromatography
86 (GC) and GC/mass spectrometry. Alkenone-based SSTs are calculated following Müller
87 et al. (1998). Isorenieratene concentrations were determined following Hopmans et al.
88 (2005).

89 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

90 Sapropel S5 in LC21 is the most intensely developed sapropel known from the
91 Pleistocene, with C_{org} concentrations up to 14% and a thickness of ~120 cm (Fig. DR1),

92 deposited over a period of ~5 k.y. (e.g., Rohling et al., 2002). The absence of benthic
93 fossils, the preserved sedimentary lamination in several intervals, and the occurrence of
94 specific biomarkers (see below) together indicate euxinic conditions in the Aegean water
95 column during S5 deposition. In the absence of bioturbation, the great thickness of S5 in
96 LC21 allows very high sampling resolution.

97 We compare our results for S5 from Aegean core LC21 with those from open
98 eMed ODP Site 971A (Fig. 1). Using the statistical multi-proxy correlation approach for
99 records through S5 (Cane et al., 2002; Rohling et al., 2002), the LC21 record has been
100 transferred onto the 971A-equivalent depth scale that serves as a master depth-scale for
101 S5 in the open eMed (Appendix DR1 and Fig. DR1). This method allows a direct
102 comparison between signals recorded in Aegean core LC21 and those in open eMed ODP
103 Site 971A, with a vertical uncertainty of less than ± 1 cm ($1\sigma = \pm 0.83$ cm) within S5 on
104 the 971A-equivalent depth scale. This correlation indicates an exact coincidence of the
105 two cores' large shift to light $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ near the onset of S5 (Fig. 2B). Given the basin's
106 prevalent wind-driven surface circulation and the proximity of the two sites (<300 km),
107 such a large and abrupt signal is indeed expected to be synchronous within the 40 ± 20 yr
108 temporal resolution of our record. We are therefore confident that our statistical method
109 constrains the correlations well within the 1σ bounds for this crucial segment of the
110 records.

111 Our chronology for S5 relies on a simple linear interpolation between the
112 estimated ages of the onset and termination of the associated light $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ anomaly
113 (Rohling et al., 2002), suggesting that, within S5, 1 cm corresponds to $\sim 40 \pm 20$ yr in
114 LC21 and $\sim 200 \pm 80$ yr in 971A (Appendix DR1). The sediment mass accumulation rate

115 (SMAR) in LC21 exceeds that in 971A by 5 times. Given this SMAR difference and that
116 C_{org} concentrations reach 14% in LC21 compared to 7% in 971A, it appears that the C_{org}
117 burial flux during S5 deposition was a full order of magnitude higher in the Aegean Sea
118 than in the open eMed.

119 Figure 2 shows the signals through S5 in LC21 along with their counterparts in
120 ODP Site 971A (all data on the common 971A depth scale). At both sites, the absolute
121 $\delta^{18}O_{pachyderma}$ values are virtually identical (Fig. 2C). This supports the previous notion
122 that the isotopic composition of *N. pachyderma* reflects basin-integrated property
123 changes, suggesting a habitat in (top) intermediate waters deriving from a single source
124 region (Rohling et al., 2004). In Aegean core LC21, changes in $\delta^{18}O_{ruber}$ appear to closely
125 track $\delta^{18}O_{pachyderma}$ within S5, which contrasts with strong variable offsets between
126 $\delta^{18}O_{ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}O_{pachyderma}$ in 971A (Fig. DR2). The $\delta^{18}O_{ruber}$ represents near-surface
127 conditions in the summer mixed layer (Rohling et al., 2004), and the similarity between
128 $\delta^{18}O_{ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}O_{pachyderma}$ in LC21 suggests that both species inhabited water masses
129 with rather similar properties. This would agree with modern observations that the SE
130 Aegean site of LC21 is directly in the northward flow path of Levantine surface water
131 (Theocharis et al., 2002), which derives from the area where Levantine intermediate
132 water is formed, and that the intermediate water itself reaches depths as shallow as 70 m
133 in the Aegean due to prevailing northerly winds and the basin's general cyclonic
134 circulation (Poulos et al., 1997; Pinardi and Masetti, 2000; Zervakis et al., 2004). Work
135 on the Holocene period of S1 deposition indicates similar conditions during times of
136 decreased eMed net evaporation (Myers et al., 1998; Casford et al., 2002).

137 Given that the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$ records through S5 are similar for both sites, the
138 contrast between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$ in 971A can be entirely attributed to
139 variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ signal in 971A displays lighter values (the offset
140 from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$ reaches more than 1.5‰; see Fig. DR2) and also is more variable than
141 in LC21 (Fig. 2B). Since both sites show similar SSTs (Fig. 2A), this difference in
142 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ is unlikely attributable to SST contrasts. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ differences within S5
143 contrast with the similarity of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ at the two sites before and after S5. The observed
144 differences between the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ signals within S5, along with similarity of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$
145 and SST signals in LC21 and 971A as well as other sites throughout the eMed (Rohling
146 et al., 2002), may only be explained by limited interaction between surface and
147 intermediate waters at the location of Site 971A, which is remote from the intermediate-
148 water source region.

149 Spatially, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ is lighter around the location of 971A than elsewhere in open
150 eMed (Rohling et al., 2002), as observed also for other sapropels (Rohling and De Rijk,
151 1999; Emeis et al., 2003). This pattern has been ascribed to extensive (monsoon-fuelled)
152 freshwater drainage along the wider N African margin, through currently dry river (wadi)
153 systems, supplementing – but more variable than – Nile river discharge (Rohling et al.,
154 2002, 2004; Scrivner et al., 2004). Remarkably, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ values in the brief interval of
155 reduced discharge (Rohling et al., 2002) from the wider N African margin (56–52 cm in
156 971A) fall back to the typical $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ values found throughout S5 in LC21 (Fig. 2B).
157 This suggests that the Aegean record reflects an underlying $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ controlled by less
158 intense freshwater dilution that may reflect propagation through the basin of the surface
159 freshening caused by N African river input into the open eMed (Rohling et al., 2002;

160 Scrivner et al., 2004). Superimposed on this widespread ‘average’ mixed signal, the large
161 regional $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ anomalies found in the open eMed (notably around 971A) would reflect
162 more direct impacts of the river-borne monsoon floods.

163 LC21 and 971A simultaneously reach the lightest $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ values, some $650 \pm$
164 250 yr after the sharp $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ shift that marks the onset of freshwater flooding into the
165 basin (Fig. 2B). This peak in eMed sea surface freshening coincides with the appearance
166 of very light $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ values (lighter by $\sim 2\%$ than $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{ruber}$; Fig. DR2) at both sites,
167 following ~ 400 yr of near absence of this species throughout the eMed (Rohling et al.,
168 2006). The shift to light $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ values, observed in both records, has been
169 suggested to reflect the proximity of a subsurface reservoir of isotopically light
170 metabolized carbon to the subsurface habitat of *N. pachyderma* (Rohling et al., 2006). At
171 the same level in LC21, high concentrations appear of isorenieratene ($>9\mu\text{g/g}$ sed.), a
172 specific aromatic carotenoid of anaerobic, photolithotrophic green sulfur bacteria
173 (Chlorobiaceae) (Fig. 2G). These bacteria require both sulphide and light (Repeta et al.,
174 1989; Koopmans et al., 1996; Passier et al., 1999). Similar to the reconstruction for the
175 open eMed (Rohling et al., 2006), the abrupt appearance of high isorenieratene
176 concentrations in the Aegean Sea, combined with the occurrence of sub-thermocline
177 foraminiferal species (e.g., *N. pachyderma*), reflects the development of euxinic
178 conditions throughout the Aegean water-column up to ~ 200 m. Comparison of LC21
179 with 971A (Fig. 2G) illustrates that such conditions had developed in the Aegean Sea
180 some 100 ± 40 to 300 ± 120 yr before they became established in the open eMed.

181 A clear sequence of causes and effects can now be summarized for the last
182 interglacial episode of freshwater flooding into the eMed. Given that benthic azoic

183 conditions and a sharp C_{org} increase developed immediately following the onset of
184 surface freshening (from one sample to the next in LC21), we infer that Aegean
185 ventilation collapsed completely within 40 ± 20 yr in response to the change in
186 hydrological forcing, even though most of the hydrological change was driven by
187 monsoon flooding into the open eMed rather than centered on the Aegean Sea. Increased
188 preservation of C_{org} due to oxygen starvation (Moodley et al., 2005), first at the sea floor
189 and then rapidly throughout the water column (Bianchi et al., 2006), would (partly)
190 explain the large jump in the C_{org} record (Fig. 2F). Within ~650 yr, euxinic conditions
191 expanded through the Aegean water column to depths of 200 m or less, fuelling
192 populations of Chlorobiaceae, with concomitant shoaling of the reservoir of isotopically
193 light metabolized carbon into the habitat of *N. pachyderma*. Some 100–300 yr later,
194 euxinic conditions reached similar depths in the open eMed (Fig. 2G).

195 **CONCLUSIONS**

196 Our results highlight an intriguing similarity in the timescale of Aegean response
197 to climatic forcing between the recent and the last interglacial events. In the mid-1960s,
198 construction of major dams (e.g., Aswan High Dam) initiated a relatively long-term
199 (estimated 80 yr) adjustment in the basin to the effects of enhanced net evaporation
200 (Rohling and Bryden, 1992). This has been proposed as an important multi-decadal
201 preconditioning for the modern eMed hydrographic changes (Boscolo and Bryden, 2001;
202 Skliris and Lascaratos, 2004; Skliris et al., 2007). Here we find that another dramatic
203 Aegean-focused response occurred during the last interglacial within a similar period of
204 time (less than 40 ± 20 yr), although this concerns a perturbation in the eMed freshwater
205 budget of the opposite sign.

206 Combined with the instrumental record of the EMT, our findings for the S5 period
207 highlight an exceptional sensitivity of the Aegean to changes in wider eMed climatic
208 forcing of any sign, with responses that lead to profound hydrographic adjustments that
209 subsequently propagate throughout the open eMed, and which potentially affect even the
210 North Atlantic (Millot et al., 2006). Both increases (preconditioning modern changes) and
211 decreases (this study) in eMed net evaporation are found to drive basin-scale
212 reorganisations in subsurface water-mass dynamics, with extensive ecological impacts.

213 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

214 This study has been supported by the UK Natural Environmental Research
215 Council, Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research, and Institute for Coastal
216 Marine Environment, National Research Council. H. Brinkhuis, B. D'Argenio, M.
217 Ribera d'Alcalà, A. Lotter and three anonymous reviewers helped to improve the
218 manuscript. We thank M. Bolshaw, E. Hopmans and J. Ossebaar for their assistance.
219 This study contributes to the Marine Science and Engineering Doctorate, Federico II
220 University, Naples, Italy, and to MEDCLIVAR.

221 **REFERENCES CITED**

222 Béthoux, J.-P., Gentili, B., and Tailliez, D., 1998, Warming and freshwater budget
223 changes in the Mediterranean since the 1940s: Their possible relation to the
224 greenhouse effect: *Geophysical Research Letters*, v. 25, p. 1023–1026, doi:
225 10.1029/98GL00724.
226 Bianchi, D., Zavatarelli, M., Pinardi, N., Capozzi, R., Capotondi, L., Corselli, C., and
227 Masina, S., 2006, Simulations of ecosystem response during the sapropel S1

- 228 deposition event: *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, v. 235, p.
229 265–287, doi: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2005.09.032.
- 230 Boscolo, R., and Bryden, H., 2001, Causes of long-term changes in the Aegean Sea deep
231 water: *Oceanologica Acta*, v. 24, p. 519–527, doi: 10.1016/S0399–1784(01)01172–0.
- 232 Cane, T., Rohling, E.J., Kemp, A.E.S., Cooke, S., and Pearce, R.B., 2002, High-
233 resolution stratigraphic framework for Mediterranean sapropel S5: defining temporal
234 relationships between records of Eemian climate variability: *Palaeogeography,*
235 *Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, v. 183, p. 87–101, doi: 10.1016/S0031–
236 0182(01)00461–8.
- 237 Casford, J.S.L., Rohling, E.J., Abu-Zied, R., Cooke, S., Fontanier, C., Leng, M., and
238 Lykousis, V., 2002, Circulation changes and nutrient concentrations in the late
239 Quaternary Aegean Sea: A nonsteady state concept for sapropel formation:
240 *Paleoceanography*, v. 17, p. 1024, doi: 10.1029/2000PA000601, doi:
241 10.1029/2000PA000601.
- 242 Emeis, K.-C., Schulz, H., Struck, U., Rossignol-Strick, M., Erlenkeuser, H., Howell,
243 M.W., Kroon, D., Mackensen, H., Ishizuka, S., and Oba, T., 2003, Sakamoto, and T.,
244 Koizumi, I., 2003, Eastern Mediterranean surface water temperatures and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
245 composition during deposition of sapropels in the late Quaternary:
246 *Paleoceanography*, v. 18, p. 1005, doi: 10.1029/2000PA000617, doi:
247 10.1029/2000PA000617.
- 248 Hopmans, E.C., Schouten, S., Rijpstra, W.I.C., and Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., 2005,
249 Identification of carotenals in sediments: *Organic Geochemistry*, v. 36, p. 485–495,
250 doi: 10.1016/j.orggeochem.2004.10.001.

- 251 Kim, S.T., and O'Neil, J.R., 1997, Equilibrium and nonequilibrium oxygen isotope
252 effects in synthetic calcites: *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, v. 61, p. 3461–
253 3475, doi: 10.1016/S0016–7037(97)00169–5.
- 254 Klein, B., Roether, W., Manca, B.B., Bregant, D., Beitzel, V., Kovacevic, V., and
255 Luchetta, A., 1999, The large deep water transient in the eastern Mediterranean:
256 *Deep-Sea Research: Part 1*, v. 46, p. 371–414, doi: 10.1016/S0967–0637(98)00075–
257 2.
- 258 Koopmans, M.P., Köster, J., Van Kaam-Peters, H.M.E., Kenig, F., Schouten, S.,
259 Hartgers, W.A., De Leeuw, J.W., and Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., 1996, Diagenetic and
260 catagenetic products of isorenieratene: Molecular indicators for photic zone anoxia:
261 *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, v. 60, p. 4467–4496, doi: 10.1016/S0016–
262 7037(96)00238–4.
- 263 Malanotte-Rizzoli, P., and Hecht, A., 1988, Large-scale properties of the eastern
264 Mediterranean: a review: *Oceanologica Acta*, v. 11, p. 323–335.
- 265 Malanotte-Rizzoli, P., Manca, B.B., Ribera d'Alcala, M., Theocharis, A., Brenner, S.,
266 Budillon, G., and Ozsoy, E., 1999, The Eastern Mediterranean in the 80s and in the
267 90s: the big transition in the intermediate and deep circulations: *Dynamics of*
268 *Atmospheres and Oceans*, v. 29, p. 365–395, doi: 10.1016/S0377–0265(99)00011–1.
- 269 Millot, C., Candela, J., Fuda, J.L., and Tber, Y., 2006, Large warming and salinification
270 of the Mediterranean outflow due to changes in its composition: *Deep-Sea Research:*
271 *Part 1*, v. 53, p. 656–666, doi: 10.1016/j.dsr.2005.12.017.
- 272 Moodley, L., Middelburg, J.J., Herman, P.M.J., Soetaert, K., and de Lange, G.J., 2005,
273 Oxygenation and organic-matter preservation in marine sediments: *Direct*

- 274 experimental evidence from ancient organic carbon-rich deposits: *Geology*, v. 33, p.
275 889–892, doi: 10.1130/G21731.1.
- 276 Müller, P.J., Kirst, G., Ruhland, G., von Storch, I., and Rosell-Mélé, A., 1998,
277 Calibration of the alkenone paleotemperature index $U^{k'}_{37}$ based on core tops from
278 the eastern South Atlantic and the global ocean (60°N-60°S): *Geochimica et*
279 *Cosmochimica Acta*, v. 62, p. 1757–1772, doi: 10.1016/S0016-7037(98)00097-0.
- 280 Myers, P.G., Haines, K., and Rohling, E.J., 1998, Modelling the paleo-circulation of the
281 Mediterranean: The last glacial maximum and the Holocene with emphasis on the
282 formation of sapropel S1: *Paleoceanography*, v. 13, p. 586–606, doi:
283 10.1029/98PA02736.
- 284 Passier, H.F., Bosch, H.-J., Nijenhuis, I.A., Lourens, L.J., Bottcher, M.E., Leenders, A.,
285 Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., De Lange, G.J., and De Leeuw, J.W., 1999, Sulphidic
286 Mediterranean surface waters during Pliocene sapropel formation: *Nature*, v. 397, p.
287 146–149, doi: 10.1038/16441.
- 288 Pinardi, N., and Masetti, E., 2000, Variability of the large scale general circulation of the
289 Mediterranean Sea from observations and modelling: a review: *Palaeogeography*,
290 *Palaeoclimatology*, *Palaeoecology*, v. 158, p. 153–173, doi: 10.1016/S0031-
291 0182(00)00048-1.
- 292 Poulos, S.E., Drakopoulos, P.G., and Collins, M.B., 1997, Seasonal variability in sea
293 surface oceanographic conditions in the Aegean Sea (eastern Mediterranean): an
294 overview: *Journal of Marine Systems*, v. 13, p. 225–244, doi: 10.1016/S0924-
295 7963(96)00113-3.

- 296 Roether, W., Manca, B.B., Klien, B., Bregant, D., Georgopoulos, D., Beitzel, V.,
297 Kovacevic, V., and Luchetta, A., 1996, Recent changes in Eastern Mediterranean
298 Deep Waters: *Science*, v. 271, p. 333–335, doi: 10.1126/science.271.5247.333.
- 299 Repeta, D.J., Simpson, D.J., Jørgensen, B.B., and Jannasch, H.W., 1989, Evidence for
300 anoxygenic photosynthesis from the distribution of bacteriochlorophylls in the Black
301 Sea: *Nature*, v. 342, p. 69–72, doi: 10.1038/342069a0.
- 302 Rohling, E.J., and Bryden, H.L., 1992, Man-induced salinity and temperature increases in
303 western Mediterranean Deep Water: *Journal of Geophysical Research*, v. 97, p.
304 11191–11198.
- 305 Rohling, E.J., and De Rijk, S., 1999, The Holocene Climate Optimum and Last Glacial
306 Maximum in the Mediterranean: the marine oxygen isotope record: *Marine Geology*,
307 v. 153, p. 57–75, doi: 10.1016/S0025–3227(98)00020–6.
- 308 Rohling, E.J., Hopmans, E.C., and Sinninghe Damsté, J.S., 2006, Water column
309 dynamics during the last interglacial anoxic event in the Mediterranean (sapropel
310 S5): *Paleoceanography*, v. 21, p. PA2018, doi: 10.1029/2005PA001237, doi:
311 10.1029/2005PA001237.
- 312 Rohling, E.J., Cane, T.R., Cooke, S., Sprovieri, M., Bouloubassi, I., Emeis, K.-C.,
313 Schiebel, R., Kroon, D., Jorissen, F.J., Lorre, A., and Kemp, A.E.S., 2002, African
314 monsoon variability during the previous interglacial maximum: *Earth and Planetary
315 Science Letters*, v. 202, p. 61–75, doi: 10.1016/S0012–821X(02)00775–6.
- 316 Rohling, E.J., Sprovieri, M., Cane, T.R., Casford, J.S.L., Cooke, S., Bouloubassi, I.,
317 Emeis, K.C., Schiebel, R., Rogerson, M., Hayes, A., Jorissen, F.J., and Kroon, D.,
318 2004, Reconstructing past planktic foraminiferal habitats using stable isotope data: a

- 319 case history for Mediterranean sapropel S5: *Marine Micropaleontology*, v. 50, p. 89–
320 123, doi: 10.1016/S0377–8398(03)00068–9.
- 321 Samuel, S., Haines, K., Josey, S., and Myers, P.G., 1999, Response of the Mediterranean
322 Sea thermohaline circulation to observed changes in the winter wind stress field in
323 the period 1980–1993: *Journal of Geophysical Research*, v. 104, p. 7771–7784, doi:
324 10.1029/1998JC900130.
- 325 Scrivner, A., Vance, D., and Rohling, E.J., 2004, New neodymium isotope data quantify
326 Nile involvement in Mediterranean anoxic episodes: *Geology*, v. 32, p. 565–568,
327 doi: 10.1130/G20419.1.
- 328 Skliris, N., and Lascaratos, A., 2004, Impacts of the Nile River damming on the
329 thermohaline circulation and water mass characteristics of the Mediterranean Sea:
330 *Journal of Marine Systems*, v. 52, p. 121–143, doi: 10.1016/j.jmarsys.2004.02.005.
- 331 Skliris, N., Sofianos, S., and Lascaratos, A., 2007, Hydrological changes in the
332 Mediterranean Sea in relation to changes in the freshwater budget: A numerical
333 modelling study: *Journal of Marine Systems*, v. 65, 400–416,
334 doi:10.1016/j.jmarsys.2006.01.015.
- 335 Stratford, K., and Haines, K., 2002, Modelling changes in Mediterranean thermohaline
336 circulation 1987–1995: *Journal of Marine Systems*, v. 33–34, p. 51–62, doi:
337 10.1016/S0924–7963(02)00052–0.
- 338 Theocharis, A., Klein, B., Nittis, K., and Roether, W., 2002, Evolution and status of the
339 Eastern Mediterranean Transient (1997–1999): *Journal of Marine Systems*, v. 33–34,
340 p. 91–116, doi: 10.1016/S0924–7963(02)00054–4.

341 Zervakis, V., Georgopoulos, D., Karageorgis, A.P., and Theocharis, A., 2004, On the
342 response of the Aegean sea to climatic variability: a review: *International Journal of*
343 *Climatology*, v. 24, p. 1845–1858, doi: 10.1002/joc.1108.

344 Ziveri, P., Ruten, A., de Lange, G.J., Thomson, J., and Corselli, C., 2000, Present-day
345 coccolith fluxes recorded in central eastern Mediterranean sediment traps and surface
346 sediments: *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, v. 158, p. 175–195,
347 doi: 10.1016/S0031–0182(00)00049–3.

348 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

349 Figure 1. Map of the Mediterranean showing the main patterns of surface circulation
350 (gray arrows), the sites of eMed dense water formation (shaded areas) (Pinaridi and
351 Masetti, 2000) and locations (black dots) of core LC21 (35°40'N; 26°35'E; 1522 m water
352 depth) and ODP Site 971A (33°43'N; 24°41'E; 2026 m water depth). Aeg. Sea = Aegean
353 Sea; Lev. Sea = Levantine Sea; Ad. Sea = Adriatic Sea; Ion. Sea = Ionian Sea.

354

355 Figure 2. Geochemical proxies through S5 in LC21 (black lines and symbols) and 971A
356 (gray lines and symbols). A: alkenone-based SST reconstructions. Alkenones are today
357 produced by coccolithophores that bloom in winter/spring in the eMed (Ziveri et al.,
358 2000). SST axis is calibrated relative to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ axis so that every 1 °C change in
359 temperature corresponds to 0.23‰ in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Kim and O'Neil, 1997). B and C: $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
360 records for *G. ruber* and *N. pachyderma*, respectively. D and E: $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records for *G. ruber*
361 and *N. pachyderma*, respectively. Isotopic records (B, C, D, and E) were lowess
362 smoothed (solid lines) (tension 0.04 and 0.05, respectively). F: Organic carbon contents.
363 G: Isorenieratene abundances. All profiles are plotted versus the 971A-equivalent depth

364 scale. Grey shaded area and dashed lines represent the visual extent of the dark-colored
365 sapropel S5 sediments in 971A and in LC21, respectively. Dotted inset identifies the
366 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ruber}}$ (heavy) anomaly in core 971A (Rohling et al., 2002). The age scale (right) is
367 based on linear interpolation between the estimated ages of 124 and 119 ka B.P. for the
368 depletion and enrichment trends in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ruber}}$ preceding and following the S5 onset and
369 end, respectively.

370

371 ¹GSA Data Repository item 2007xxx, **Supplementary Information on stratigraphic**
372 **framework and chronology**, is available online at

373 www.geosociety.org/pubs/ft2007.htm, or on request from editing@geosociety.org or

374 Documents Secretary, GSA, P.O. Box 9140, Boulder, CO 80301, USA.

375

376

377

378

379

380

381

382

383

384

385

386

387 Figure 1

388

389

390

391

392

393

394

395

396

397

398

399

400

401

402

403

404 Figure 2

405

406